

Toward End-to-End Visual Active Tracking for MAVs

Alberto Dionigi

Simone Felicioni

Mirko Leomanni

Gabriele Costante

Abstract—Visual active tracking is an increasingly explored research field in robotics due to its crucial role in applications like human assistance, disaster recovery, and surveillance. Contrary to passive tracking, active tracking methods merge together vision and control capabilities to detect and actively track the target. While most of the works in this area concentrate on ground robots, the limited contributions on aerial platforms still pose noteworthy design challenges that hinder their applicability. To tackle these issues, in this extended abstract we introduce our ongoing work D-VAT [1], a novel end-to-end method for active visual tracking. It relies on deep reinforcement learning and is specifically tailored for micro aerial vehicles. The D-VAT system computes the vehicle thrust and angular velocity commands directly from data captured by a single monocular camera. We show that this approach allows for precise and collision-free tracking maneuvers, outperforming multiple state-of-the-art baselines in simulated environments that differ significantly from the training settings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro aerial vehicles (MAVs) have garnered growing attention thanks to their agility and affordability, which make them suitable for multiple robotic applications. In this study, we focus on the visual active tracking (VAT) task, which requires a *tracker* vehicle to maintain visual contact with a moving and non-cooperative *target*. In contrast to passive tracking, where the pose of the camera is fixed, active tracking approaches actively regulate the camera pose by suitably controlling the vehicle, ensuring the target remains within the camera field-of-view (FoV). Although previous research on this problem combined a dedicated perception module (e.g., an object tracker [2]) with a separate control module for the vehicle motion, more recent works are exploring Deep Reinforcement Learning to develop end-to-end solutions for VAT [3], [4], [5], [6]. However, most of the works in literature focus only on ground robots and can take advantage of the physical characteristics of these platforms, while the very few contributions devoted to more complex platforms (such as MAVs) still rely on some simplifying assumptions, e.g., by ignoring the vehicle dynamics [7] or by limiting the control actions to a predefined subset of the action space [8].

Clearly, solutions based on these simplifications are, in general, less robust and performing. Consequently, we aim to remove these assumptions and propose D-VAT, a novel end-to-end DRL-based continuous control model for visual active tracking that is tailored to MAV systems. D-VAT relies on a monocular setup, i.e., it requires only an RGB image stream collected by an onboard camera to directly compute the thrust and angular velocity commands needed to track the target with high accuracy.

The authors are with the Department of Engineering, University of Perugia, 06125 Perugia, Italy {alberto.dionigi, simone.felicioni}@studenti.unipg.it, {mirko.leomanni, gabriele.costante}@unipg.it.

Fig. 1. Overview of the VAT task. The *tracker* MAV (blue) adjusts its position and orientation so as to keep the *target* MAV (red) at the center of the camera FoV and at a predefined distance. Our approach exploits an end-to-end DRL-based VAT method that directly maps RGB images into thrust and angular velocity commands that are fed to the tracker.

II. APPROACH

The goal of VAT is to control the motion of a tracker agent equipped with a vision sensor, so as to maintain the target within the FoV of the camera and at a predefined distance. In this paper, we assume that both the tracker and the target are MAVs that are free to move in 3D. The vision sensor is an RGB camera and the tracker employs only its image stream to compute the thrust and angular velocity commands needed to meet the control goal.

Similarly to other complex navigation and control tasks, VAT can be tackled by formulating a suitable reinforcement learning problem and exploiting Deep Neural Network (DNN) approximators. In particular, we adopt an *asymmetric actor-critic* formulation [6] and we design two different DNN architectures for the *actor* (A-DNN) and for the *critic* (C-DNN). The former learns the optimal policy with respect to the given task, while the latter aims to evaluate such a policy during the training phase. The asymmetric structure of this framework allows the critic network to be fed with more privileged information than the actor network, since the A-DNN is the only agent operating at inference time.

The A-DNN is composed of a convolutional neural network and a multi layer perceptron (MLP). The former processes a sequence of three front-view camera images and extracts the corresponding visual features, while the latter employs those features to compute the action. On the other hand, the C-DNN design consists only of a MLP block, which is fed with the position, the velocity and the acceleration of the target with respect to the tracker, in order to estimate the *action-value* function.

To build a simulated environment suitable for training the DRL agent, we employ Unreal Engine 4 (<https://www.>

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS IN THE BOX ENVIRONMENTS AND IN THE PHOTOREALISTIC SCENARIOS (URBAN, PARK AND OFFICE)

Method	Experimental Scenarios and Metrics															
	Box Environments				Urban				Park				Office			
	P_θ	P_φ	P_ρ	P_c	P_θ	P_φ	P_ρ	P_c	P_θ	P_φ	P_ρ	P_c	P_θ	P_φ	P_ρ	P_c
AOT [3]	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03
AD-VAT+ [4]	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
C-VAT [5]	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04
SiamRPN++ [2] LQG	0.27	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.10	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.37	0.27	0.27	0.30	0.11	0.08	0.09	0.09
SiamRPN++ [2] PID	0.65	0.65	0.55	0.62	0.57	0.56	0.46	0.53	0.94	0.93	0.76	0.88	0.78	0.75	0.67	0.73
D-VAT (Our)	0.94	0.94	0.86	0.91	0.94	0.94	0.91	0.93	0.95	0.95	0.92	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.86	0.92

unrealengine.com), a popular graphics engine that provides advanced photorealism capabilities. We built a large furnished room and we exploit *domain randomization* [9] to facilitate the development of the robustness and generalization capabilities needed to directly deploy the DRL agent in more complex photorealistic environments. In particular, at beginning of each training episode, the room characteristics are randomly altered in light conditions, furniture, and texture patterns, including those of walls and floors.

III. EXPERIMENTS

Our approach is tested on two environment classes: the first one contains scenes similar to those used during the training phase, although with different room shapes, objects disposition, and textures (we refer to these scenes as Box Environments). The second is, instead, aimed at testing the generalization capabilities of D-VAT and has more complex and photo-realistic environments, *i.e.*, an outdoor urban scenario (Urban), an outdoor park environment (Park), and an indoor scene of an office building (Office).

The D-VAT agent is compared with several SotA baselines. More specifically, we considered (i) end-to-end DRL-based approaches that employ both discrete (**Active Object Tracking** (AOT) [3], **AD-VAT+** [4]) and continuous (**C-VAT** [5]) action spaces, and (ii) modular strategies that combines the object tracker SiamRPN++ [2] with two standard MAV control architectures (**SiamRPN++ PID** and **SiamRPN++ LQG**). Furthermore, to properly evaluate the performance of the different methods in a MAVs scenario, we adapted the tracking metrics described in [5], [6] to a 3D environment. In particular, the **Distance Score** (P_ρ) measures the ability of the tracker to maintain the desired distance from the target, while the **Elevation Score** (P_θ) and the **Azimuth Score** (P_φ) measure respectively the ability of the tracker to maintain the target vertically and horizontally aligned to the center of the FoV, and the **Total Score** (P_c) it is the arithmetic mean of the above metrics.

The results of the experimental campaign are presented in Table I. D-VAT outperforms all the baselines with respect to the performance metrics, and it is able to track the target by producing low-level control commands directly from RGB images. Furthermore, thanks to the domain randomization strategy we employ, this holds even when the visual conditions of the environment are very different from those employed in the training phase.

The learning-based approaches AOT, AD-VAT+ and C-VAT fail to converge to a suitable tracking policy. This could be explained by considering the high complexity of the task. On the other hand, the baselines that combine two separate modules, *i.e.*, an object tracker and a classic controller (LQG or PID), are instead able to achieve better results. Nonetheless, the overall tracking performance is inferior to that of D-VAT. This can be attributed to the modular nature of these baselines. As the two components are designed independently, their coupling turns out to be inefficient and can cause the overall system to fail.

IV. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

Currently, D-VAT can track vehicles whose appearance is similar to that of the target MAV used for the optimization. Future work will consider methodologies to make the tracker agent independent from the appearance of the target MAV.

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